

Change Readiness Among Employees in a Private Educational Institution: Basis for Strategic Change Management

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Abstract

This study assesses the level of change readiness among employees in a private educational institution, highlighting its role in ensuring successful organizational change. Using Macachor's (1999) framework, the study focused on six key dimensions of change readiness: track record of change, expectations of change, attitude toward change, top management support, acceptability of change, and structures for change. A quantitative-descriptive design was employed with a validated survey instrument administered to purposively selected teaching and non-teaching personnel. Results revealed an overall high level of readiness, particularly in

structural support and top management engagement, while attitude toward change was rated only average, indicating a need to address internal resistance. Moreover, statistically significant differences in change readiness were observed when respondents were grouped according to sex, age, and length of service. In light of the results, the study put forward proposed strategies to improve change management processes with a focus on participation, strategic communication, and targeted actions contributing towards a more resilient, adaptive and forward-looking educational institution.

Keywords: *Change Readiness, Attitude to Change, Top Management Support, Structures for Change, Change Management*

INTRODUCTION

The ancient philosopher Heraclitus once said, *everything is in constant flux*. This statement holds true in most if not in all aspects of our lives. Even in corporate and organizational settings, change remains inevitable. Especially with the rapid pace of change in today's competitive environment, pressure emerges within organizations which must be confronted and dealt with accordingly (Metwally, et al, 2019).

Change is a constant force in organizations, including educational institutions, where rapid technological advances, shifting stakeholder expectations, and competitive pressures demand continuous adaptation (Metwally et al., 2019; Seggewiss et al., 2019). For schools, the challenge is not only to implement changes but to ensure that employees are ready to accept and sustain them.

Because it reflects the institution's structural capacity as well as the employees' willingness to participate in change initiatives, change readiness is a crucial component of a successful transformation (Wijaya, Sutojo, & Wijaya, 2024). While much research has examined organizational change in general, less attention has been given to private educational institutions in the Philippine context, where demographic factors and institutional culture may strongly influence readiness. This study addresses this gap by assessing employees' readiness for change across six dimensions—track record of change, expectations of change, attitude toward change, top management support, acceptability of change, and structures for change (Macachor, 1999)—and identifying strategies to enhance institutional adaptability.

As stated by Macachor (1999), change readiness can be measured using six dimensions namely; institution's track record of change, expectations of change, attitude to change, top management support, acceptability of change and structures for change. First, the track record of change refers to the communal experience in managing change in the past. This includes individual recall of details of the change, the degree of success and the acceptance and impact of the change. Second, expectations of change is defined as how well the expected outcomes of change have been communicated and constantly understood by the involved members of the organization. The third dimension of change is attitude to change which is the tendency and disposition to continuously search and recognize opportunities for improvement, the practice of regularly reviewing how things are done, the encouragement of creativity and initiative, and the confidence to try new ideas and challenge tradition. Fourth, the top management support refers to the school managements' eagerness to support change, categorized by the commitment of significant resources and effectiveness of performance. Fifth is the acceptability to change which looks into the significance of the planned change in the institutional development plan, the extent to which they make the job more fulfilling and rewarding, and whether the change can be easily implemented or not. Lastly, structure for change refers to facets in the schools' environment that will cultivate successful change management, such as self-managed teams, a functional management information system, opportunities to express ideas, a performance management system and the applicable leadership style.

Although there are many different definitions of change readiness among academics, most agree that it represents an organization's ability and its members' willingness to accept change. Weiner (2020) highlights the idea of change valence, or the perceived value of the change to employees, while Shea et al. (2013) define it as the degree to which people are psychologically and socially ready to accept organizational changes. Despite differences in terminology, these definitions all emphasize the three interconnected aspects of readiness—behavioral, affective, and cognitive.

The cognitive dimension of readiness refers to how employees understand and interpret the need for change. It entails acknowledging the gap between intended future results and existing practices and having faith that suggested modifications are suitable for the objectives of the organization (Armenakis & Harris, 2002; Palmer, Dunford, & Akin, 2016). Employees are more likely to see change as both necessary and possible when expectations are clearly stated and in line with institutional goals.

The affective dimension relates to the emotional responses of employees toward change. Openness to new practices is fostered by positive attitudes like optimism and trust in leadership, whereas resistance can be triggered by fear, uncertainty, or perceived threats (Jansen, Ship, & Michael, 2015; Lizar, Mangundjaya, & Rachmawan, 2015). Employee attitudes regarding innovation, reorganization, or new

policies have a significant impact on whether they will actively support or oppose initiatives in educational institutions. Therefore, being prepared involves more than just having a logical understanding; it also involves developing healthy emotional engagement.

The behavioral dimension concerns the actual capacity and actions taken by employees to implement change. This encompasses flexibility, involvement in projects, and faith in group effectiveness (Weiner, 2009). Behavioral readiness is strengthened by structural supports like open communication channels, training opportunities, leadership support, and clear policies (Davis & Fifolt, 2018). Employees are more likely to convert readiness into tangible actions that maintain transformation when they believe that leadership is dedicated and resources are available.

By synthesizing these perspectives, the literature shows that change readiness is a comprehensive concept that encompasses knowledge, feelings, and behavior rather than being a disjointed idea. Because of this, the current study places Macachor's (1999) six indicators— track record of change, expectations of change, attitude toward change, top management support, acceptability of change, and structures for change—within these more general parameters. This synthesis provides a structured foundation for analyzing how employees of private educational institutions perceive and enact readiness for change.

In order to develop strategies for a context-responsive change management initiatives in the institution, this study looks into the level of change readiness among its employees evaluating their perceptions across the six key dimension.

Specifically, the study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of change readiness of the respondents in terms of the following dimensions:
 - 1.1. institution's track record of change;
 - 1.2. expectations of change;
 - 1.3. attitude to change;
 - 1.4. top management support;
 - 1.5. acceptability of change; and
 - 1.6. structures for change?
2. Is there a significant difference in the change readiness of the respondents when they are grouped according to the following demographic profile:
 - 2.1 sex;
 - 2.2 age;
 - 2.3 marital status; and
 - 2.4 length of service?
3. What strategies for change management can be proposed based on the results of the study?

Objectives of the Study

This study evaluates the change readiness of employees in a private educational institution by analyzing the following six dimensions: the institution's track record of change, expectations of change, attitude toward change, top management support, acceptability of change, and structures for change. It also aims to find out if employees' change readiness varies significantly when categorized by demographic profile, specifically sex, age, marital status, and length of service. In addition, the study aims to develop change management strategies customizing the support provided to the institution's employees during organizational transitions based on the findings.

Hypothesis of the Study

H₁ There is no significant difference in the change readiness of the respondents when they are grouped according to demographic profile

FRAMEWORK

The focus of this research on change readiness among the employees of a private educational institution is anchored on Weiner's Theory of Organizational Readiness for Change (2009), where he defines organizational readiness as a mental state within a system where its constituents are willing to undertake change and believe that they can successfully achieve it. Weiner's organizational readiness definition incorporates the change valence; the value of the change and its resource availability and task demands. Weiner believed that the issue of change readiness is multifaceted, intertwining personal and organizational factors. It includes:

- **Change Commitment** (the shared resolve to implement change),
- **Change Efficacy** (the shared belief in collective capability to implement the change).

The framework by Armenakis & Harris (2002) that was cited in the introduction of the study says that individual change readiness derives from:

- **Discrepancy (recognition of the need for change),**
- **Appropriateness (belief that the change is suitable),**
- **Efficacy (belief in capability to succeed),**
- **Principal support (belief that management is supportive),**
- **Valence (perceived personal benefit of the change).**

The six dimensions applied in this study are drawn from Macachor's (1999) paradigm and may be described as follows:

1. **Track Record of Change** – relates to past success influencing change efficacy.
2. **Expectations of Change** – aligns with discrepancy and anticipated outcomes.
3. **Attitude to Change** – reflects personal valence and emotional readiness.
4. **Top Management Support** – connects to principal support.
5. **Acceptability of Change** – corresponds with perceived appropriateness and valence.
6. **Structures for Change** – supports implementation efficacy and reduces uncertainty.

This study specifically uses Macachor's (1999) six dimensions as its guiding framework because it is contextually grounded in the Philippine educational setting, despite the fact that there are other models of change readiness. Macachor's framework was created and approved in a local academic institution, in contrast to more general international models like Weiner's (2009) theory of organizational readiness or Armenakis and Harris' (2002) five-component model. This makes it especially relevant for analyzing the unique dynamics of private educational institutions in the Philippines, where organizational culture, leadership practices, and employee demographics differ significantly from Western contexts. Additionally, the cognitive, affective, and behavioral components of readiness are balanced in Macachor's dimensions—track record of change, expectations of change, attitude toward change, top management support, acceptability of change, and structures for change—while still being useful for quantitative evaluation. This

framework guarantees methodological coherence, cultural appropriateness, and direct applicability to the institutional realities being studied.

In addition, the present study also applies the Individual Differences Theory in organizational behavior by investigating how specific demographic factors including age, sex, educational attainment, civil status, and length of service influence employees' organizational perceptions and reactions to change (Madsen et al., 2005; Furxhi et al., 2022).

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study

The paradigm presents the variables used in this study. These variables are (1) demographic profile in terms of sex, age, marital status and length of service and (2) change readiness which will be measured based on track record of change, expectations of change, attitude to change, top management support, acceptability to change and structures to change. It illustrates that the effect of demographic variables on the level of change readiness of the employees will be determined. The output data of the study will determine the practical strategies for change management which may be adopted by private educational institutions.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study adopts a quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational approach. The descriptive aspect of the study will assess the level of change readiness among the employees across various dimensions, while the correlational aspect will explore whether there are any significant differences in change readiness when grouped according to demographic characteristics.

Participants

The target population for this study includes employees of a private educational institution in the Philippines. This includes faculty, administrative staff, and other personnel who are involved in the day-to-day operations of the institution.

A stratified random sampling technique was used to ensure that all relevant sub-groups (e.g., faculty vs. administrative staff) are represented in the sample. This method allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the varying levels of change readiness across different types of employees.

There is a total of 98 teaching and 53 non-teaching personnel. From the total population of 151, the study only included a sample of 123 respondents which was computed using G*Power. The participants were limited to full-time and part-time faculty members (pre-school to college) and non-teaching personnel. Employees from third party agencies such as janitors and security guards were not included as participants in the study.

Instruments

The instrument used in the study consisted of two parts, Part I – Demographic Profile and Part II – Change Readiness.

Part one, identify participants' sex, age, educational attainment, marital status, and length of service in the institution.

Part Two assessed the change readiness of the participants. This part of the instrument was adapted from the study of Macachor (1999). This was designed to measure positive indicators for successful introduction of change considering the school's track record of changes, expectations of change, attitude to change, top management support, acceptability of change and structures for change. Under each consideration, the respondents were asked to complete certain statements based on five possible choices ranked from one to five, with the statement ranked five as the most likely positive indicator of extreme readiness for change.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher requested permission to conduct the study and distribute the questionnaire to the intended participants in a letter sent to the school president, vice president for academics and research, and vice president for administration of the chosen private educational institution prior to the data collection.

Data was collected using a structured survey questionnaire adopted from Macachor (1999) to measure the six dimensions of change readiness. The survey will include both Likert-scale items and demographic questions to gather data on gender, age, employment status, civil status, and length of service.

Two weeks were allotted for the dissemination and retrieval of the surveys, which were completed using Google Forms. In order to increase response rates, participants were given a specific amount of time to finish the questionnaire, and reminders were sent out at specific times. The survey instrument took only ten to fifteen minutes to complete by the participants. There was a provision of safe space for both the participants and the researcher as the responses can be solely accessed by the researchers only. Data were downloaded in aggregate form using the Excel application. It was then forwarded to the statistician for tabulation and statistical analysis.

Data Analysis

Means, frequencies, and percentages were utilized to describe the demographic profile of the study participants. To determine the participants' level of change readiness across its various dimensions, the same statistical techniques were used, along with standard deviation.

To determine whether there is a significant difference in the participants' level of change readiness when grouped according to their demographic profile, Anova and the T-Test for Independent Samples were employed.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical guidelines were followed throughout the study to ensure participant anonymity, informed permission, and responsible data handling. The administration's consent was obtained before any data was gathered.

RESULTS

Table 1. Level of Change Readiness

Level of Change Readiness	Mean	Sd	Verbal Interpretation
Track Record of Change	3.81	.677	High
Expectation of Change	3.74	.853	High
Attitude to Change	3.27	.626	Average
Top Management Support	3.95	.822	High
Acceptability to Change	3.76	.945	High
Structure to Change	4.05	.819	High
Overall Mean	3.76	.614	High

Legend : Range of Values

1.00 – 1.79
 1.80 – 2.59
 2.60 - 3.39
 3.40 – 4.19
 4.20 – 5.00

Level of Change Readin

Very Low
 Low
 Average
 High
 Very High

Table 1 shows the level of change readiness among respondents across various dimensions: Track Record of Change, Expectation of Change, Attitude to Change, Top Management Support, Acceptability to Change and Structure to Change.

The results revealed that the level of Change Readiness of respondents is “high” with an overall mean of 3.76. Among the dimensions, the highest rating was in Structure to Change with a mean score of 4.05 (High), followed by Top Management Support with a mean score of 3.95 (High), Track Record of Change with a mean score of 3.81 (High), Acceptability to Change with a mean score of 3.76 (High) and Expectation of Change with a mean score of 3.74 (High). Among the six dimensions, attitude to change had the lowest score of 3.27, categorized as “Average”.

Table 2. Difference in the level of change readiness of respondents when grouped according to demographic profile

Demographic Variable		Mean	Standard Deviation	F-statistics	P-value	Remarks
Sex	Male	3.96	.398	12.674	0.001	Accept H_1
	Female	3.60	.707			
Age	21-30 years old	4.02	.463	6.204	0.001	Accept H_1
	31-40 years old	3.91	.545			
	41-50 years old	3.67	.558			
	51 years old and above	3.44	.716			
Marital Status	Single	3.81	.610	.450	.639	Reject H_1
	Married	3.70	.628			
	Widowed	3.72	.495			
Length of Service	Less than 1 year	4.167	.463	14.730	.000	Accept H_1
	1-3 years	4.04	.455			
	4-6 years	3.74	.251			
	7-10 years	3.70	.000			
	11-15 years	3.93	.441			
	16-20 years	3.61	.313			
	21-25 years	3.44	.568			
	26-30 years	2.82	.649			
31 years and above	2.56	.017				

Table 2 examines the differences in the level of change readiness among various demographic groups. The alternative hypothesis (H_1), that there is a significant difference in the level of change readiness when participants are grouped according to demographic (in terms of sex, age, marital status and length of service) are tested. A probability value (p-value) less than 5 % or 0.05 margin of error for the results would mean accepting the alternative hypothesis (H_1). This means that there is a significant difference when the respondents are grouped according to demographic profile. On the other hand, the p-value of more than 0.05 would mean rejecting the alternative hypothesis. By rejecting the alternative hypothesis, the research hypothesis that there is a significant difference when the respondents are grouped according to demographic profile is thereby not accepted. The p-value of less than 0.05 would mean significant correlation while the p-value of less than 0.01 would mean highly significant correlation. Results revealed that sex, age, and length of service are significantly correlated with their level of change readiness as indicated with the p-values which are all less than 0.05.

DISCUSSION

Level of Change Readiness

Findings of the study suggest that respondents generally exhibit high level of change readiness particularly in the dimensions Structure to Change, Top Management Support, Track Record of Change, Acceptability to Change and Expectation of Change. Only the dimension Attitude to Change garnered an average rating.

All facets of the organization's resources, structures, and strategy could be impacted by change. The result shows that the structures of change in the institution influence other members of the community. This is dissimilar to the study of Davis & Fifolt (2018) which acknowledged that they "lack authority to influence" other members of their communities to accept changes in their higher education institutions. Participants in their study felt that introducing change is challenging due to a variety of stakeholder groups, institutional silos, outcome control, and a lack of team member buy-in. Additionally, they acknowledged that some of their colleagues disliked change initiatives because they believed that "what had worked in the past would continue to work in the future."

Gfrerer et al (2021) asserted, however, that decentralization might be a part of the organizational structure. It may be necessary for administrators or leaders to modify their approaches based on the organization's requirements and the best way to carry them out. They must be adaptable, particularly if the objectives call for modifications.

Therefore, it is necessary to develop a strong disposition for change. However, for a change to be effective, all members of the organization must participate holistically. Strengthening the organization's members' involvement in quality-related activities is essential (Gfrerer et al, 2021).

Change in the organization can be implemented if there is an enthusiastic top management support. The foregoing study also revealed that top management support is high. This implies that the top management or the administrators have the commitment to change and can commit the significant resources for change (Armenakis & Bedeian, 1999; Eby et al., 2000 cited in Sadarić & Škerlavaj, 2023 and Wijaya, Sutojo, & Wijaya, 2024). Top managers can provide resources and be supportive to the change management program. With the top management support, the need for change can be easily resolved. Hence, the acceptability of the entire organization to change affects the outcomes of the implemented changes (Seggewiss, et al, 2019).

In the process of the change, it is necessary to examine the institution's *track record of changes*. As the study revealed a high level in this dimension, it indicates that the institution finds the importance of self-assessment of both the external and internal environments to determine the positive and negative forces and drivers for an organization. Management of change should begin with questioning the organization's history of successful change and of key individual's awareness of the need to change (Palmer, Dunford, & Akin (2016).

Consequently, the institution finds tracking the record of changes is part of the first stage of the cycle of changes. The challenges and issues need to be recognized, as Carnall & By (2014) indicate. As a result, awareness is raised. Studies on feasibility and diagnosis have begun. The experiences and views of the organizations on change are taken into account. These all contribute to the development of achievable performance in the dynamic environment. The main goal is to raise awareness of the organizations' current circumstances. The process of recognition and awareness is maintained. According to Devos et al. (2007 cited in Metwally, et al, 2019), the individual's successful and positive change history within the organization seems to have a favorable impact.

The process of transformation or change may be viewed favorably or unfavorably. In this study, acceptability to change is high. The results of changes are influenced by how well-received they are by the entire organization (Crandall, 2015). This infers that change is welcomed proactively for it is believed that it is essential for the organization to continue evolving. The way of acceptance is reactive, nevertheless, if it is perceived as a danger to the organization's social and cultural norms. People become resistant to change if they believe it would undermine their stability. Because it may introduce change and be met with resistance, it is critical that the organization's top management evaluates each person's and organization's preparation for change (Sadarić & Škerlavaj, 2023).

Once the plan for change is introduced, there are expectations that arise. This study found out that the expectations to change in the institutions is high which implies that there are prospects of what will happen and where it will lead to. Armenakis & Harris (2002) and Bernerth, (2004) cited in Lizar, Mangundjaya, & Rachmawan, (2015) stated that change readiness requires clarification. Moreover, according to Mello (2015: 259), "change involves disrupting the status quo and entering areas of uncertainty." It is the reason why the need for change should be clarified as to assess the organization's readiness for change.

However, the dimension attitude to change is average which is the lowest among the dimensions. This infers that the institution should give further attention to improve the area on attitude to change. Armenakis & Harris (2002) and Bernerth, (2004) cited in Lizar, Mangundjaya, & Rachmawan, (2015) stated that change readiness requires clarification of attitudes towards change. Members of the organization must have the attitude of readiness for change. According to Lyons (2009) and Holt (2007) cited in Lizar, Mangundjaya, & Rachmawan, (2015), the personnel's attitude of readiness for change is an inclusive and comprehensive attitude that is encouraged simultaneously with the content, which refers to what is being changed; with the process, which denotes how the change is being applied and employed; with the context, which is the condition or situation under which the change is occurring, and with the individuals, which bring up the qualities of the persons concerned in the change process. Eby et al. (2000) cited in Lizar, Mangundjaya, & Rachmawan, (2015) claimed that personal and job attitudes stimulate change readiness. They also held that working in team or group and trust in one another develop change readiness.

Different studies conducted by Gentles-Gibbs & Kim (2019), Metwally, et al (2019) and Wijaya, Sutojo, & Wijaya (2024) stressed that the personnel's attitudes and viewpoints are significant in the implementation of change. If employees possess the mental and social skills necessary to accept and embrace organizational change, thus, they are ready for change. An organization's readiness for change can be determined by how eager and willing it is to embrace and use new concepts. Therefore, for these changes to have a good impact, the organization must have positive acceptance. To ensure organizational preparedness, the institution's staff needs to be adaptable and quick to change.

Attitude on change readiness is directed by individual scheme. Hence, individual preparedness leads to organizational change. From the individual level to the collective level, this mindset spreads. Employees' attitudes toward change—whether they are open to innovation or resistant to it—can significantly influence the effectiveness of institutional development (Lizar, Mangundjaya, & Rachmawan, 2015 and Wijaya, Sutojo, & Wijaya (2024)).

Change Readiness and Demographic Profile

The study found that all demographic profiles are significantly correlated with Organizational Citizenship Behavior except for marital status.

Differing viewpoints among various sexes might influence how change is received generally. The foregoing study result is similar with Mardhatillah & Rahman (2020) in which significant difference was established between male and female employees and their change readiness. In their study, male employees are readier for change than female employees. According to Vakola et al. (2003), referenced in Mardhatillah & Rahman (2020), one possibility for the discrepancy is that male employees are more receptive to various circumstances and more emotionally firm than female employees. Because of this, male employees are more adaptable. This is also supported by the studies of Patom & Damster (2002) and Tyler (2005), Madsen, et al. (2005) and Shah (2009) cited in Furxhi, Stillo & Teneqexhi (2022), that male and female varies in change readiness. However, Morrison, Oladunjoye & Rose (2008) in their study cited in Furxhi, Stillo & Teneqexhi (2022) found out that women are more skillful in solving work place issues and in bringing about organizational change. Hence, women are more competent in establishing trust and relationships.

This is dissimilar to the studies of Lizar, Mangundjaya, & Rachmawan, (2015) and Wittension (2008) cited in Mardhatillah & Rahman (2020) in which it was found out that there was no significant difference across gender and the change readiness of the employees.

As to age and change readiness, the result is similar to the studies of Madsen, et al. (2005) and Shah (2009) cited in Furxhi, Stillo & Teneqexhi (2022) that there is a significant difference in the level of change readiness across various age groups. Furthermore, the study of Mardhatillah & Rahman (2020) established that there was a significant difference across different ages and the employees' change readiness. It was revealed that older employees are readier for change than younger employees. It was believed that these old employees have more dependents than younger employees (Shah & Sha, 2010 cited in Mardhatillah & Rahman, 2020). Hence, being family-oriented, it was difficult for these old employees to leave the organization if they do not like the change initiatives. Moreover, Roebbers & Schneider (2010), referenced by Bashir et al. (2021) state that employees' ideas of what should be focused on their work tasks vary as they get older. According to the work demand model, Bashir et al. (2021) emphasized that employees place greater value on the inherent aspects of their employment as they get older. However, Bashir et al.'s (2021) study found that younger workers prefer job-crafting activities over older workers, suggesting that younger workers are more adaptable than older workers.

Alternatively, another study revealed a different result, Lizar, Mangundjaya, & Rachmawan, (2015) found out that there are no differences between groups based on age in relation to change readiness.

Marital status is an often overlooked demographic factor that can influence an employee's readiness for change within an organization. Employees' personal circumstances, such as being married, single, or having dependents, can affect their emotional resilience, flexibility, and ability to engage with change initiatives. For instance, employees with significant family responsibilities may face greater challenges in adapting to changes that require additional time commitments or relocation. Shah (2009) cited in Furxhi, Stillo & Teneqexhi (2022) emphasized that there is a significant difference in marital status and change readiness. People's readiness for change may be influenced by their marital status, with single people showing higher levels of willingness than married people.

Nonetheless, the result of this study revealed that there is no significant difference between marital status and change readiness. This is similar to the result of the study of Abou shahba, Shazl., & Abd Elhamid (2023) which elucidated that employees' awareness of the importance of the change process is not related to marital status. This is also supported by Mderis, et al. (2024) where marital status and overall organizational preparedness for change was not statistically significant. Marital status is external and does not directly alter these cognitive beliefs unless linked with contextual family stressors which is individual-specific and not generalizable.

The study showed that there is a significant relationship between length of service and change readiness. The result agreed with Madsen, et al. (2005) and Shah (2009) cited in Furxhi, Stillo & Teneqexhi (2022) that there was discernible difference between change readiness and personnel with shorter service durations and those with longer service durations. Long-term employees and new hires are not equally open to change. In Mardhatillah & Rahman (2020), Sinha & Rajpal (2002) state that workers with more years of service are less willing to embrace organizational changes. Accordingly, younger workers that are change-oriented typically have shorter service durations. In addition, Bashir et al., (2021) clarified that members who have recently joined the organization or who have less experience tend to have more recent knowledge and skills and have higher expectations than members who have more years or more experience.

Hence, employee length of service is a significant demographic component that affects how prepared an organization is for change because long-serving staff members may have developed habits, relationships, and a strong bond with the current culture. The knowledge and comfort with present procedures may make these long-serving personnel more resistant to change. Conversely, younger workers might be more receptive to change since they are less enmeshed in the company's historical procedures. Gaining insight into the tenure distribution of employees enables leaders to customize their change management tactics, providing longer-tenured staff with more assistance and guaranteeing more seamless transitions for everyone. Understanding the different needs depending on length of service promotes a more successful and inclusive transition process (Mardhatillah & Rahman, 2020).

Proposed Strategies for Change Management

Based on the findings of the study, the following strategies are presented to strengthen institutional change readiness and ensure more effective change implementation:

1. Enhance Employees' Attitude Toward Change

The institution should prioritize initiatives that foster transparency, flexibility, and trust in the change process, as "attitude to change" received the lowest rating (Mean = 3.27, read as Average).

- Conduct regular capacity-building seminars to increase capacity in the areas of innovation, adaptability, and change psychology.
- Promote a culture of participation and feedback by utilizing open platforms and channels for idea sharing.
- Establish programs for recognizing employee who demonstrate effective adaptability to change.

2. Strengthen Communication of Change Expectations

Despite having a high score (Mean = 3.74), "expectation of change" is nevertheless one of the lowest among the dimensions. The goal, procedure, and anticipated outcomes of change should all be communicated with clarity and consistency.

- Send out change-related notifications using a range of media, including bulletin boards, town halls, and email.
- Establish a Change Communication Team to ensure that information is clarified and transmitted on time.

3. Sustain and Leverage Top Management Support

Maintaining and formalizing leadership involvement in change programs is crucial, especially considering the high score for top management support (Mean = 3.95).

- Engage leaders in advancing particular change initiatives.
- Request regular reporting of change implementation milestones from leadership teams.

4. Institutionalize Structural Support for Change

Given that the "structure for change" category scored the highest (Mean = 4.05), the institution should establish systems that have made this strength possible.

- Include change management practices in strategic planning and human resources policies.
- Keep giving functional teams and units the authority to create and carry out locally relevant change solutions.

5. *Customize Interventions Based on Demographics*

Age, sex, and duration of service should all be taken into account when designing programs because they have a big impact on change readiness:

- Give younger employees and those with shorter tenure access to innovation labs and training in change leadership.
- For senior or long-tenured employees, offer them personalized coaching, include them in mentoring, and acknowledge their contributions to prior advancements.
- Create gender-sensitive training materials and safe spaces to promote equitable participation in change initiatives.

6. *Develop and Implement a Formal Change Management Program*

Implement a structured program that institutionalizes change readiness through training, monitoring, leadership, and communication based on the study's findings.

7. *Monitor and Evaluate Change Readiness Regularly*

Establish a biannual or annual change readiness survey to monitor developments, spot new gaps, and modify interventions as necessary.

8. *Promote a Culture of Continuous Improvement*

Include indicators of change readiness in performance reviews and unit scorecards.

- Conduct team meetings, retreats, and reflection exercises to promote ongoing dialogue about change.

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to evaluate employees' change readiness within a private educational institution through Macachor's (1999) six dimensions: track record of change, expectations of change, attitudes to change, top management support, acceptability to change, and structures to change. The research revealed that employees demonstrated substantial change readiness across domains involving structural support mechanisms and top management support. The institution has established foundational elements essential for executing change initiatives successfully.

However, the results also uncovered that the attitude toward change dimension achieved merely an average rating which suggests that despite existing institutional procedures some employees remain reluctant or uncertain about embracing change. The necessity for increased focus on employee psychological and personal preparedness emerges as a critical consideration. Statistically significant differences in change readiness emerged across age, sex, and length of service categories which demonstrates the necessity for tailored change management approaches to address the distinct requirements of various employee subgroups.

The study's outcomes emphasize how institutional structures combined with workforce viewpoints and demographic variety contribute to establishing a change-ready environment. The study's conclusions serve as an initial foundation to create change management strategies that are evidence-based while also being inclusive and culturally sensitive. Through targeted initiatives to boost change readiness, the institution will develop greater adaptability and resilience while advancing its forward-thinking capabilities to meet the shifting educational demands.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Several strategic recommendations can be made to support and maintain change initiatives based on the results of the study. According to this research, even though the organization exhibits a generally high degree of change readiness across a number of dimensions, including acceptability, top management support, and change structures, it is still imperative to enhance employees' attitudes toward change. The organization should give priority to initiatives that promote optimistic thinking and emotional fortitude in order to address this. This includes structured opportunities for feedback and discussion where employees feel heard and appreciated during changes, as well as professional development centered on flexibility and transparency.

Additionally, change-related communication tactics need to be improved and organized. Even though "expectation of change" received a comparatively high rating, the results indicate that it could be improved. A thorough internal communication plan must guarantee that all employees understand the purpose, advantages, and progression of suggested changes. Participatory meetings, visual progress dashboards, and frequent briefings can all help achieve this. Additionally, employees may be designated as change agents or ambassadors to localize and cascade information, enhancing the clarity and ownership of change initiatives across departments.

The institution needs to implement inclusive and focused interventions because of the notable differences in change readiness by sex, age, and length of service. For example, innovation labs and change leadership training may be well received by new and younger employees, whereas tenured employees might be delegated as mentors or their prior contributions can also be acknowledged to gain their support. To guarantee equitable engagement and participation in change initiatives, gender-sensitive practices and programs should also be put into place. These focused strategies will boost motivation, lessen resistance, and foster a climate of mutual dedication.

Lastly, it is advised to establish a structured, long-term change management program. This should involve leadership development based on emotional intelligence and inclusive decision-making, integration of change readiness indicators into performance management systems, and routine monitoring and assessment via organized surveys or readiness audits. By doing this, the organization can establish a long-lasting culture of continuous improvement and establish itself as adaptable and resilient in a constantly changing educational environment.

The results of the study can be used to develop practical strategies to increase flexibility in private educational institutions. Administrators can keep the high levels of change readiness in top management engagement and structural support and address the weaker area – employee attitude to change – through targeted engagement and training initiatives. The findings support the development of differentiated interventions based on age, sex, and length of service to ensure inclusivity and effectiveness. Change readiness indicators can also be embedded in leadership training, performance reviews and strategic planning. Overall the study provides a good foundation to promote a culture of resilience and continuous development, to prepare educational institutions to navigate change more effectively.

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